

ORGANIZATIONAL AND LEGAL FOUNDATIONS OF SPECIAL PREVENTION MEASURES AMONG PREVIOUSLY CONVICTED PERSONS

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Abstract. This article highlights the organizational and legal foundations for implementing special prevention measures among previously convicted persons by prevention inspectors. Additionally, proposals and recommendations have been developed regarding the theoretical and practical aspects of special preventive measures implemented among previously convicted persons, as well as solutions to problems arising in the mechanism of law enforcement.

Keywords: crime prevention, prevention inspector, previously convicted persons, special prevention, measures, legal framework.

The effective organization of preventive work among previously convicted persons by prevention inspectors and ensuring meaningful leisure activities for minors and young people, as well as raising the legal awareness and culture of previously convicted persons, serve to prevent the influence of various negative trends and the commission of crimes in mahallas. As a result of this work, over the past five years, nearly twenty percent of neighborhoods in our country have not experienced any crime. Furthermore, as a result of collaborative efforts, the proportion of extremely serious and serious crimes within the structure of all crimes is decreasing.

Naturally, the prevention inspector working in our republic also plays a significant role in achieving such results. Today, the emerging risks and threats, primarily international terrorism, religious extremism, illegal migration, human trafficking, and the increasing spread of ideas alien to our people among youth, are setting new tasks for internal affairs bodies to prevent and eliminate them in a timely manner. This requires the effective organization and improvement of activities of our country's internal affairs bodies, particularly their prevention inspectors and previously convicted persons. Moreover, the lack of targeted and comprehensive approach to crime prevention measures and combating crime, as well as the absence of systematic development of effective measures to identify and eliminate the causes and conditions contributing to offenses, indicate the existence of several problems and shortcomings in organizing and managing crime prevention activities between internal affairs prevention inspectors and previously convicted individuals.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-5005 of April 10, 2017, "On Measures to Fundamentally Enhance the Effectiveness of the Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies, Strengthen Their Responsibility for Ensuring Public Order, Reliable Protection of the Rights, Freedoms, and Legitimate Interests of Citizens"[1] acknowledges that work on offense prevention primarily consists of combating the consequences of committed unlawful acts. It recognizes the insufficient organization of systemic and effective measures for early prevention of offenses, in-depth analysis, identification, and elimination of their causes and

conditions. The decree also outlines tasks that need to be implemented to address these shortcomings.

Therefore, crime prevention is carried out not through criminal law punishments, but through the early prevention of crime, the identification of causes and conditions for its commission, and the application of mitigation measures, which require knowledge and analysis of events, phenomena, and processes in all spheres of public life that contribute to crime prevention.

Today, reforms in the field of crime prevention are being intensively continued, the legal framework for the development of the sphere has been improved, measures have been taken to improve the material and technical base, especially to provide it with new innovative information technologies, and work has been carried out in this direction.

One of the important tasks is to improve the activities of the prevention inspector in the organization and implementation of crime prevention among previously convicted persons, to attract new forces and means in this process.

Systematic work is also being carried out to provide preventive activities with qualified specialists and improve the quality of work in this area. As a result, the implementation of the prevention of offenses among previously convicted persons by the prevention inspector has become a guarantee, first of all, of maintaining peace and tranquility, law and order and public safety in mahallas, villages, towns and auls. At the support point of the internal affairs bodies, employees of the relevant branch services of the internal affairs bodies serve in close cooperation with each other, citizens' self-government bodies and other public structures, as well as other bodies of state power.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 5005 "On Measures to Fundamentally Enhance the Effectiveness of the Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies, Strengthen Their Responsibility for Ensuring Public Order, Reliable Protection of the Rights, Freedoms, and Legitimate Interests of Citizens" (April 10, 2017) [2] addresses serious shortcomings and problems in the activities of internal affairs bodies, including crime prevention, particularly in managing the activities of internal affairs support points and prevention inspectors. The decree emphasizes that current risks and threats, primarily international terrorism, religious extremism, illegal migration, human trafficking, and the increasing spread of ideas alien to our people among the youth, have posed new tasks for internal affairs bodies to prevent and eliminate these issues in a timely manner. Consequently, several tasks were set for them, including the timely elimination of causes and conditions leading to offenses, increasing the legal culture of all segments of the population, instilling respect for the law and intolerance to any manifestation of law-breaking, and ensuring early prevention of offenses as the most important task.

Therefore, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-4947 "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" (February 7, 2017) [3] stipulates special attention to be paid to the system of crime prevention and the fundamental improvement of the activities of internal affairs bodies in combating crime and maintaining public order.

In addition, during the ongoing reform process, methods of implementing the tasks assigned to internal affairs bodies regarding the organization of crime prevention are studied and communicated. These tasks are clearly defined in the decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-2896 dated April 18, 2017 "On measures to fundamentally improve the activities of crime prevention units of internal affairs bodies" defines the most important task of internal affairs bodies as qualitatively improving the activities of crime prevention services, establishing their specific areas of activity; improving cooperation with the public, early prevention of offenses, shaping citizens' legal awareness and culture, preventing offenses among minors and youth, protecting them from various negative influences; improving the activities of prevention inspectors, establishing systematic reporting to the public; developing and implementing effective criteria for evaluating the performance of prevention inspectors; widespread application of modern information and communication technologies in the field of crime prevention, improving the system of developing professional knowledge and skills of prevention inspectors.

The laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Youth Policy" (2016), "On Internal Affairs Bodies" (2016), "On Combating Corruption" (2017), "On Administrative Supervision of Certain Categories of Persons Released from Penitentiary Institutions" (2019), "On Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence" (2019), "On Prevention and Treatment of Narcological Diseases" (2020), decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Strategy for Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" (2017), "On measures to fundamentally increase the effectiveness of internal affairs bodies, strengthen their responsibility in ensuring public order, reliable protection of citizens' rights, freedoms and legitimate interests" (2017), "On approval of the Public Security Concept of the Republic of Uzbekistan and measures for its implementation" (2021), resolutions "On measures to further improve the system of crime prevention and combating crime" (2017), "On measures to fundamentally improve the activities of crime prevention units of internal affairs bodies" (2017) and other legislative acts related to the field serve to increase the effectiveness of ensuring their implementation to a certain extent.

References:

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